

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-AWARENESS AND PARENTAL BEHAVIOR IN IMPLEMENTING TOILET TRAINING IN TODDLER-AGE CHILDREN

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Abstract

The toddler period is a period of intensive environmental exploration because children are trying to find out everything that is happening, a problem that often arises during this period is difficulty controlling urination. Efforts that can be made to overcome this problem include toilet training. One of the factors that influences toilet training is self-awareness. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between self-awareness and parental behavior in toilet training toddlers. The method used in this study is quantitative correlation with a cross-sectional approach. The sample used was mothers who had toddlers totaling 164 people, using self-awareness instruments and toilet training behavior that had been tested for validity using the Pearson Product Moment correlation test on 30 respondents with the results of 29 questions containing 24 valid statements and on the behavioral instrument from 11 all questions were declared valid. The reliability test used Alpha Cronbach with the results of self-awareness at 0.909 and maternal behavior at 0.880 ($r_{\text{alpha}} > r_{\text{table}}$). Univariate analysis produces distribution and percentage, bivariate analysis uses the Spearman rank test with independent variables of self-awareness and dependent variables of behavior in toilet training in toddlers. The results showed that most respondents had low self-awareness (51.8%) and low behavior (54.9%). There is a relationship between self-awareness and toilet training behavior ($p\text{-value} = 0.014$). The self-awareness that mothers have can help control emotions and self-perception when toilet training children. It is hoped that health workers can intensively provide education to mothers who have toddlers do toilet training.

Keywords : Self Awareness, Toilet Training, Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

The toddler period is from 12 to 36 months of age, which is a time of intensive exploration of the environment as the child tries to figure out how everything works. This can be a very challenging time for both parent and child as each learns to know each other better; this is a crucial period for achieving Child development and growth [1]. Various problems that arise during the toddler period are about the function of child growth and development [2]. According to the Ministry of Health 2019, the quality of toddler growth and development in Indonesia needs serious attention in terms of getting good nutrition, adequate stimulation, and accessibility to quality health services, including early detection and intervention of growth and development deviations [3]. Development during the toddler period is a change from the phase of trust and distrust to the phase of autonomy, which is indicated by an increasingly broad attitude of independence [4]. During this period, children can control their body parts, their language skills increase, and they are in the anal phase where children begin to be able to control defecation and urination. The tasks of social and emotional development in toddlers include children showing independence by starting to learn toilet training, which is influenced by the child's physical, mental, and social development [5].

Various problems that arise during the toddler period are about the function of growth and development of children [2]. One of the problems that often arises in toddlers is difficulty in controlling defecation (BAB) and urination (BAK); this can occur until preschool age. According to the National Household Health Survey (SKRT), it is estimated that the number of toddlers who have difficulty controlling defecation and urination in toddler to preschool age reaches 75 million children [6]. Bad habits in controlling defecation and urination will cause bad things in children in the future, can cause children to be undisciplined and spoiled, and most importantly, later on, children will experience psychological problems, feel different, and cannot independently control defecation and urination..

Efforts that can be made to overcome this are toilet training for children, which is an effort to train them to be able to control defecation and urination. Toilet training can generally be carried out on every child who has started to enter the independence phase; this phase is usually in children aged 18-36 months [7]. *Toilet training carried out at an early age will foster independence in children to channel their physiological needs* [8]. The purpose of toilet training is so that children are able to control defecation and urination. Toilet training is also useful in early sex education because by doing toileting, children will learn about their own body functions.

Children who are not taught toilet training will be at risk of experiencing urinary tract infections (UTIs), urinary incontinence, and enuresis (bedwetting) [7]. This can be caused by a lack of knowledge and behavior of mothers about how to train for defecation and urination, the use of disposable diapers (diapers) [9], this is in line with research conducted [10] which states that failure in toilet training is influenced by negative maternal attitudes, not motivated to do toilet training because they assume using diapers is more effective and instant so that mothers do not feel bothered. In addition, research conducted by Lutviyah [11] states that there is a relationship between parental behavior and the ability to toilet train in toddlers.

Research conducted by Murhadi, T. [12] shows that there are three dominant factors causing toilet training failure, namely how to teach toilet training, emotional readiness, and parenting patterns. Other factors that can affect children not being able to control their bowel movements and urination or failure in toilet training are influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors are drives that come from within a person in the form of knowledge, parenting patterns, and parental attitudes, while extrinsic factors are in the form of facilities and infrastructure and the environment [2], In addition, toilet training failure is also caused by parents who are not aware of the importance of toilet training, do not have the heart to train their children, or the parents' laziness to train [13].

The impact of parents who do not do toilet training on children will make children become less independent and still carry the habit of bedwetting; children are less sensitive to their surroundings so that children defecate and urinate in random places, which can affect the success of toilet training [14] Children who do not undergo toilet training can experience various negative impacts, both physical and psychological. Physical impacts include digestive disorders such as constipation, urinary tract infections, and bladder control problems, while psychological impacts can include shame, low self-esteem, and difficulty interacting socially. In addition, delays in toilet training can also cause children to become less independent and have trouble adapting to the environment outside the home [15]. The benefits of toilet training on children are the formation of real independence in children because children are used to doing things like defecating and urinating themselves, a sense of shame will arise in children, and usually children do not want to be considered small children anymore. Children will understand personal hygiene, such as knowing that they are dirty, so they are used to washing their hands and anus after defecating and urinating and maintaining the cleanliness of the toilet. Children can know the parts of the body and their functions.

The concept of toilet training is not widely understood in society; this is because information related to toilet training is not generally introduced in society so that toilet training is considered not very important in the child's development stage [16] This can also affect the self-awareness of parents or mothers in teaching children about toilet training. In Indonesia, cases of children who still wet the bed up to the age of 6 years reach 12%. This is due to the lack of awareness of parents or adults in teaching toilet training to children at an early age [17]. Toilet training for toddlers is quite difficult, as a child enters a stage of development in fighting doubts. Children who are 2-3 years old want emotional freedom that depends on their parents, children want to be independent in various things physically, but the task cannot be completed without guidance, so

that a phenomenon of caution arises from parents in carrying out their roles because during these times there is often a reaction of rejection from children [18].

Self-awareness is a person's self-awareness that is able to understand, accept, and manage all potentials for future life development [19]. Self-awareness in a person has the aim of knowing one's condition, strengths, and weaknesses so as not to make a mistake in deciding an action. The first step to self-awareness is getting to know yourself, because it is important to understand yourself, which can later form behavior to change [20]. Independence must be trained and developed in children as early as possible so as not to hinder the child's subsequent developmental tasks, the critical period for the development of independence occurs at the age of two to three years (toddler age), at this age the child's developmental task is to develop independence, one of the needs for autonomy is toilet training, if the need to develop independence is not met at the age of around two to three years will result in inhibition of the development of maximum autonomy. To change a person's behavior, good self-awareness is needed to increase parental awareness of the importance of toilet training [21]. To change a person's behavior, good self-awareness is needed to increase parental awareness of the importance of toilet training. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between self-awareness and parental behavior in toilet training toddlers.

2. METHODOLOGY

Self-awareness is a person's self-awareness that is able to understand, accept, and manage all potentials for future life development [16]. Self-awareness in a person has the aim of knowing one's condition, strengths, and weaknesses so as not to make a mistake in deciding an action. The first step to self-awareness is getting to know yourself, because it is important to understand yourself, which can later form behavior to change [17]. The method in quantitative correlational research is a cross-sectional approach. The population in this study was mothers who had toddler-aged children in one of the villages in Sumedang Regency, totaling 164 people, and the sampling technique was total sampling, this research was conducted in February 2023. The instruments used were self-awareness and toilet training behavior questionnaires. The self-awareness questionnaire was compiled based on aspects described by Daniel Goleman, while the behavior questionnaire used a questionnaire from Sri Fitdiyah Ningsih, which was modified and had been tested for validity and reliability. Validity test using Pearson Product Moment correlation test on 30 respondents with the results of the self-awareness questionnaire from 29 questions: there are 5 invalid statements because the r_{count} value $< r_{\text{table}}$, namely question number 1 ($r_{\text{count}} = 0.011 < 0.361$), number 7 ($r_{\text{count}} = 0.109 < 0.361$), number 9 ($r_{\text{count}} = 0.17 < 0.361$), number 16 ($r_{\text{count}} = 0.095 < 0.361$), and number 29 ($r_{\text{count}} = 0.191 < 0.361$). In the behavioral questionnaire, there are 11 questions, and all questions are declared valid. Reliability test using Alpha Cronbach with the results of the self-awareness questionnaire 0.909 and the mother's behavior questionnaire 0.880 ($r_{\text{alpha}} > r_{\text{table}}$). The data collection technique in this study was interviews and this study has obtained ethical permission from Padjadjaran University number 16/UN6.KEP/EC/2023. Univariate analysis produces distribution and percentage, and bivariate analysis uses the Spearman rank test with the self-awareness variable, and the dependent variable is parental behavior in toilet training toddlers.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Demographic Data

Table 1. Frequency Distribution Data of Respondent Characteristics (n=164)

Characteristic	Frequency (f)	Percentage (5)
Age (Years)		
17 – 25	46	28
26 – 35	83	50.6
36 – 45	26	15.9
46 – 55	9	5.5
Education		
No School	1	0.6
SD/MI	58	35.4
SLTP	55	33.5
SLTA	40	24.4
College	10	6.1
Child Age (Month)		
12 – 24	68	41.5
25 – 36	96	58.5
Child's Gender		
Man	80	48.8
Woman	84	51.2

Table 1 shows that most (50.6%) of the respondents are aged between 26-35 years, the most of the respondents' education is elementary / MI (35.4%), most (58.5%) are 25-36 months old, and the majority (51.2%) are girls.

3.2 Overview of Self Awareness and Toilet Training Behavior

Table 2. Overview of Self Awareness and Toilet Training Behavior (n=164)

Characteristic	Frequency (f)	Percentage (5)
<i>Self Awareness</i>		
Less	85	51,8
Good	79	48,2
<i>Behaviour</i>		
Less	90	54,9
Good	74	45,1

Table 2 shows that most of the respondents (51.8%) have less self-awareness, and most (54.9%) have less toilet training behavior..

3.3 The Relationship of Self Awareness to Toilet Training Behavior (n=164)

Table 3. *The Relationship between Self Awareness and Toilet Training Behavior (n=164)*

Self Awareness	Toilet Training Behavior				Total		OR (95% CI)	P value
	Less		Good		f	%		
	f	%	f	%				
Less	46	65,7	24	34,3	70	100	2,825	0,041
Good	38	40,4	56	59,6	94	100	(1,138-	
Total	84	51,2	80	48,8	164	100	7,011)	

Table 3 shows that most (65.7%) of the respondents' self-awareness and toilet training behavior are lacking and there is a relationship between self-awareness and toilet training behavior (p-value 0.041).

4. DISCUSSION

The results of the study showed that most respondents had low self-awareness. Self-awareness is the main stage in recognizing oneself and aiming to change; in addition, self-awareness is also a capacity that allows humans to observe themselves and distinguish themselves from others [22]. *Self-awareness is an ability possessed by individuals in terms of analyzing each of their thoughts so that the individual can know the impact of something before the individual does it* [23]. Someone who has good self-awareness will be able to understand the feelings that arise in themselves and understand every form of their behavior and the impact of these feelings and behavior on others, so when mothers have a good level of self-awareness, they can understand and carry out toilet training on toddlers.

Several factors that influence self-awareness, according to Bulecheck in Rizal, Z [24] are thoughts, feelings, motivation, knowledge, and environment. The results of the study showed that most self-awareness is low so that mothers feel no need to teach children to go to the bathroom since childhood because it can be learned naturally. Lack of self-awareness of mothers can cause mothers not to believe that toilet training in toddlers will make children accustomed to defecating and urinating in the right place. Self-awareness is also influenced by awareness of emotions and self-perceptions of individuals because individuals who have high self-awareness will be better able to manage emotions and self-perceptions [25]. Mothers who have high self-awareness can manage emotions and perceptions well so that they will be happy to do toilet training in toddlers. Another factor that can influence self-awareness is being aware of one's own abilities and shortcomings so that mothers will be aware of their abilities and shortcomings can help mothers to improve their skills and actions in toilet training in toddlers.

The events caused by the failure of toilet training are that there are still many young children who wet the bed, defecate, and urinate in random places, until the child enters school age, which will hurt the child's development in the future. The impacts caused by the delay in children in carrying out toilet training are that children become stubborn and difficult to control, children become spoiled, not independent, and still carry the habit of wetting the bed until they are adults. If toilet training is not applied to children from an early age, it will be more difficult to direct children when they get older. An independent attitude is one of the early childhood developments that children need to have, so that children are used to doing everything themselves. Without depending on others, but still with a little parental guidance according to their developmental stages and capacities. Children's independent attitudes need to be applied from an early age; if children's independent attitudes are applied after the child grows up, that independence will not be complete. Children prefer to do everything on their initiative rather than being served or ordered by others, but parents often hinder their children's desires and do not encourage children to be independent, so that children become more spoiled and always depend on others. Children need someone who believes in their abilities by providing the best way to learn for children, including toilet training. So, when children are independent, children can easily absorb knowledge around them through independence.[26].

The results of the study showed that most toilet training behavior was lacking. Several factors that influence behavior include age, occupation, education, knowledge, and attitude. Lawrence Green (1991) in Saputra, P. A [27]. Mother's behavior in toilet training toddlers can be influenced by several factors, one of which is the level of education and knowledge. The results of the study showed that most respondents had elementary and junior high school education. Education affects a person's knowledge and behavior so that someone with low education tends to have low knowledge. This is in line with research conducted by Wijayanti, A. R [28] which states that there is a significant relationship between maternal knowledge and behavior, where it can be explained that the higher the knowledge possessed, the better the behavior possessed by the individual; conversely, the lower the knowledge possessed, the worse the behavior possessed by the individual. Behavior is the result of all kinds of experiences and human interactions with their environment, which are manifested in knowledge, attitudes, and actions. Notoatmojo in Lutviyah [11]. Giving instructions in the form of words to children has a fairly large value in providing early stimulation. Efforts to train children in toilet training include providing instructions in the form of words before and after urinating or defecating from an early age [29]. Toilet training can be done by providing the correct example so that it is easily accepted and imitated by children [29].

The results of the study showed that there was a relationship between self-awareness and toilet training behavior. Respondents who have low self-awareness can cause mothers' toilet training behavior to be less good; this is because low self-awareness affects the failure to train children for toilet training. Self-awareness possessed by mothers can help to control emotions because mothers who have high self-awareness will be able to manage emotions and self-perceptions when toilet training their children. This can help mothers to be more patient and empathetic to children who are learning and reduce stress and anxiety that may arise in mothers during the process of teaching toilet training. Toilet training should be taught when children are still small; toilet training with oral techniques and providing examples has a significant value in providing stimulation to defecate. With this technique, the child's psychological preparation will be more mature, and finally the child will be able to defecate well. Respondents who have low self-awareness can cause mothers' behavior in toilet training to be less than good, this is because low self-awareness affects not training of children for toilet training. Self-awareness is a person's self-awareness that understands, accepts, and manages all potential for future life development [30].

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the level of self-awareness in respondents is mostly at a low level, while more than half of respondents have a low level of behavior in toilet training. There is a relationship between self-awareness and the behavior of mothers in toilet training. It is hoped that health workers can intensively provide education to mothers who have toddler-aged children to train toilet training. in children has a significant positive relationship.

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